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INFORMATION

about the acceptance of the article

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Research Focus International Scientific Journal informs you that your article, "**O' GENRI HIKOYALARINI TARJIMA QILISH PAYTIDA YO'L QO'YILGAN KAMCHILIKLAR**" (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15272033>) has been accepted for publication.

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Director of the "Ilm-fan va innovatsiyalar akademiyasi":

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